

INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR USE IN TEACHING CARDIOLOGY IN MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of a medical university founded by "cardiology" specializing in Information and communication technologies and pedagogical technologies. The article deals with the integration of educational technologies, information and pedagogical technologies, and their auxiliary content.*

Keywords: *medicine of education, future doctors, information technology, teacher of technology, communication, integration, integration of education, switching, animation.*

Introduction. Methods and tools of education are of particular importance in providing quality and guaranteed education in the educational process. It is important to use integration, i.e. integrated technologies, in the organization of the educational process at the level of modern requirements. The word integration corresponds to the Latin word "integratio" and means to restore, start again, fill. The relationship between individual parts and elements is a concept that represents their integration. The word integration is also used to express the process of rapprochement and interconnection of disciplines. The concept of integration is one of the important scientific terms, it is a methodological tool for generalization and drawing conclusions. In science and technology, general harmony models and algorithms are created between the contents of a process or events with the help of this methodological tool. The essence of integration is also of particular importance in solving the problems of ensuring harmony in the content of education provided in medical institutions of higher education. The main concepts of educational subjects taught through integration are summarized. The concept of integration is also used to establish a relationship between information on a research object and methodology. Integrated technology refers to technologies resulting from combining, generalizing and establishing connections between two or more technologies. As a result of the use of integrated technologies, training sessions are organized remotely using the capabilities of network technologies and simulation centers. This is the basis of distance learning. The main task of network technologies in distance education is to ensure communication between the teacher and the student during the educational process. The educational process organized without constant communication between the teacher and the student will not give the intended effect. In the daytime form of the educational system, communication between the teacher and the student is carried out at the same time, in the same place, in the educational auditorium. In distance education, this process is carried out through computer network technologies on the basis of telecommunication tools. The integrated state of the integrated technologies discussed above can be considered as the most optimal technology for teaching and mastering. Using the possibilities of pedagogical and information technologies, creating an information-educational environment for learners, integrated technologies of delivery processes to learners on the basis of communication technology tools is the main task of the main technologies.

Research Methodology. Integrated technologies and their use in the teaching of cardiology in medical institutions of higher education help to make the educational process effective and interactive. Below are these technologies and how they are used:

1. Simulation technologies. Simulation mannequins and manuals: Medical students can practice cardiac procedures, such as CPR or defibrillation, in a safe environment. Cardiovascular system simulators are used. It is taught to repeat different cases of patients and to prepare students for complex clinical situations.

2. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR). VR/AR training programs. Provides a 3D visualization of the anatomy and physiology of the heart, helping students better understand the complex structures. Includes clinical situations and repetitions of operations. Students can experience surgeries and clinical situations in a VR environment.

3. E-learning platforms and online courses. Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs): Online courses in cardiology offered by the world's leading universities and research centers. Interactive Learning Modules: Interactive materials that allow students to learn independently and test their knowledge.

4. Telemedicine and telemonitoring. Telemedicine Platforms: Enable real-time interaction with patients and attending consultations, remote monitoring of cardiac status and giving students hands-on experience with real patients.

5. Electronic Health Records (EHR). Working with EHR systems: Teaching students to work with patients' electronic health records, which will improve their future work efficiency. Clinical decision support systems: Use of clinical decision support systems in the diagnosis and treatment of heart disease.

6. Research technologies. Biomarkers and Genomic Analysis Technologies: Teaching students how to use modern research technologies to study and diagnose heart disease. Big Data and Artificial Intelligence: Applying Artificial Intelligence Algorithms to Analyze and Predict Big Data on Heart Disease.

7. Integration of educational programs. PBL (Problem Based Learning): Teaching students to solve complex clinical situations by integrating practical and theoretical knowledge. TIL (Team-Based Learning): Guiding students to develop teamwork and communication skills.

8. Mobile applications and training programs. Medical Calculators and Apps: Get instant information on heart disease essentials with calculators and mobile apps. Interactive tests and quizzes: Using interactive tests and quizzes to test students' knowledge.

Conclusion. Our study covers foundation, science, practice and life skills. Integrated technologies help make medical education more interactive, interesting and effective. This allows students to better acquire the skills of applying theoretical knowledge in practice.

The goal of teaching cardiology based on a creative approach in higher education institutions is limited to the goals of the SES and the curriculum, and the student cannot apply his knowledge, skills and abilities to practice. Therefore, it determines the need for a creative approach in higher education institutions.

Creative competence of students includes the following elements: acquisition of necessary knowledge, skills and abilities; personality characteristics that determine the ability to perform some activity; set of professional characteristics.

A student's ability is manifested through his creative competence. The combination of student qualities, motivation, ability can be represented as a vector and analyzed as a set of composition, knowledge, skills, abilities and competences.

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